

Figure S1. Phylogenetic time-tree with confidence intervals showing the phylogenetic separation between the Ancestral, Latin American (LA) and European (EU) clades. Strains from Ancestral, LA and EU clades are circled in gray, orange and blue color boxes respectively. X-axis represents the time in years (1965 to 2020). Scale bar represents the unit of time (years). Tips in the tree are aligned to the year of isolation of the strains. Nodes are dated in the x-axis as estimated by BEAST. Horizontal blue bars at the nodes represents 95% confidence interval for each estimate.

Figure S2. PCA plot comparing plasmid composition (plasmid contigs $\geq 50\text{Kb}$ only) of strains of *S. Paratyphi* B var. Java ST28. Data points from European, Latin American and Ancestral strains are shown in blue, orange and gray color respectively. Clusters I and II are indicated by oval rings and grouped IncI1 and IncHI2 plasmids with near identical content respectively.

